

Biology Education Students Perception of the use of Moodle-Lms for Learning

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ABSTRACT

The study evaluated how University of Ilorin biology education students felt about using Moodle-LMS for instruction. A survey-style descriptive research design was chosen. All University of Ilorin students studying biology education make up the population. For the study, a sample of 205 respondents was chosen using the random sampling technique. For the study, a questionnaire created by the researcher and verified by a test-retest reliability test was used. The results showed that there is no discernible difference in the readiness of male and female Biology Education students to adopt Moodle-LMS for learning at the University of Ilorin, or in how they perceive Moodle-LMS for learning at the institution. Additionally, Moodle-LMS should only be used to deliver appropriate lectures to students, as some courses are not satisfying. Finally, lecturers should try to incorporate the use of Moodle-LMS for delivering lectures in case of emergency, as seen during the COVID-19 pandemic.

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INTRODUCTION

Education serves as the foundation for both advanced and emerging nations. Science education is primarily interested in sharing the processes, values and content of science to the general public (Olorundare, 2023). Biology is one of the core area of specialization in science education, students who study biology education at universities are qualified to become high school teachers. In today's world, the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) is integral to the teaching and learning process. ICTs are now integrated into all stages of data collection, information processing, and knowledge creation, with teaching and learning being a prime example of this phenomenon. (Awe, 2016).

All around the globe, governments have allocated resources towards the development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). In Nigeria, traditional teaching methods have been impacted by academic and social changes as a result of the gradual integration of ICT into the learning process (Abdullah, 2018), the objective is to enhance the quality of teaching and learning in educational institutions through the application of innovative technologies. As a result, policies have been created to govern the implementation of ICT in schools. (Awe, 2016).

It is clear that the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of innovative teaching methods and technologies in African educational institutions. The closure of schools forced educators to quickly adapt to new modes of instruction, and this has led to the adoption of a variety of delivery methods to ensure that students continue to receive an education.

The use of web-based learning, e-learning platforms, CD-ROMS, television, radio, emails, and SMS services are all effective methods for delivering education to students who are unable to attend school in person. This diversity in delivery methods is important because it allows educational institutions to reach a wider range of students, including those who may not have access to the internet or other advanced technologies.

It is also notable that many African countries have adopted a blended approach to instruction, which combines online learning with broadcast methods such as television and radio. This approach recognizes the fact that not all students have access to the internet, and it also allows for a more flexible and adaptable approach to instruction.

Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic has been a catalyst for educational innovation in Africa. While the pandemic has presented significant challenges for educational institutions, it has also provided an opportunity to experiment

with new teaching methods and technologies, and to find creative ways to ensure that students continue to receive a high-quality education.

Moreover, LMS can be limited in terms of customization, making it difficult for instructors to tailor their courses to meet the needs of their students (Costello, 2013). It is also important to note that not all students have equal access to technology and the internet, which may limit their ability to fully participate in online learning (Kumar et al., 2020). Additionally, LMS can create a sense of isolation for students who may feel disconnected from their classmates and instructors (Abdullah, 2018). Despite these challenges, LMS remains a valuable tool for online learning and has proved especially useful during the COVID-19 pandemic when traditional in-person classes were disrupted. As we move forward, it will be important to continue exploring ways to enhance the capabilities of LMS and address its limitations to ensure that all students have access to high-quality online learning experiences.

Indeed, the success of online learning through LMS relies heavily on effective instructional design and pedagogy that align with the needs of the learners. It is important to acknowledge that not all students may thrive in an online learning environment and therefore require different approaches to learning (Dharmendra et al., 2017). Instructors should take into consideration factors such as learner motivation, engagement, and interaction when designing online courses through LMS. Additionally, the use of assessment tools within LMS can help instructors measure the effectiveness of their teaching and adjust their instruction accordingly (Sulun, 2018).

Furthermore, LMS can provide learners with opportunities for self-paced learning, access to course materials, and the ability to collaborate with other learners and instructors beyond the traditional classroom setting. LMS has the potential to promote active learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, which are essential in today's society (Bervell & Arkorful, 2020). Therefore, it is crucial to utilize LMS effectively to maximize the benefits of online learning while minimizing the challenges that may arise.

In summary, Learning Management Systems (LMS) are widely used in higher education to facilitate online learning, promote collaboration, and enhance teaching and learning effectiveness. While LMS has the potential to provide learners with flexible, cost-effective, and accessible learning opportunities, instructors must also consider pedagogical strategies that align with the needs of the learners to ensure effective online instruction. As LMS is also designed to be instructor-oriented, empirical findings have indicated that it restricts learners from exploring the learning facilities independently (Yılmaz, Karaoğlu, Yılmaz & Cakmak, 2017). Furthermore, its inadequacy as an effective communication and interaction platform (Abdullah, 2018) reflects substandard

opportunities as a collaborative tool (Yilmaz, Karaođlan, Yilmaz & Cakmak, 2017).

Abdullah (2018) noted learning management systems are used for both synchronous and asynchronous delivery methods in educational settings. Additionally, LMSs have been used in the following different course types and course delivery types such as, Lecture, lab, lecture and lab, practicum. Course Delivery Types: Synchronous, Asynchronous, Hybrid (Sulun, 2018). Likewise, issues were also apparent in terms of usability as older LMS versions were mainly designed for desktop-based interaction while not supporting mobile accessibility (Brophy, 2016). When a majority of Biology Education students today are avid users of smartphones (Kumar et al., 2020), the unavailability of quick mobile access and unresponsive design tends to negatively affect the success of the platform (Abdulasisi, 2021). Moreover, due to this need, factors relating to resources such as the internet, devices, and access have played a crucial role in the intention to use an information system (Zwain, 2019).

Students' engagement in academic activities on e-learning environments such as a LMS plays a vital role in contributing to their academic success. According to Kim, Hong & Song (2019), helping students to perform better using online learning environments enhances their academic engagement leading to better grades. When students actively engage and take control of their learning processes, their cognitive skills develop. Learners who take control of their online learning can engage with peers, spend time online learning and are able to utilize LMS features to learn and communicate with peers and instructors (Brophy, 2016). This implies that the actual experiences that the students go through in online learning influences their engagement and academic performance. The literature reveals that there is a significant relationship between the learning environments utilized by the students and their impact on self-regulated learning strategies (Yilmaz, Karaođlan, Yilmaz & Cakmak, 2017).

Numerous Learning Management Systems (LMS) have been launched; some are commercial software, such as WebCT and Blackboard, whereas others are open-source applications, including the Modular Object-oriented Dynamic Learning Environment (Moodle), Ilias, A Tutor and Claroline. Although all applications share common features, some offer more specific, flexible and complete features, such as role identification, assignment functionality and chat management. (Brophy, 2016). Moodle, as Hui Hsu (2012) describes, allows faculty to build dynamic and effective online learning sites for students. Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment (MOODLE) is an open-course management system that is also known as an LMS. MOODLE was introduced to assist lecturers in creating online courses that focus on interaction and collaboration, with the first version of MOODLE being released in August 2002 (Patel & Patel, 2017). According to Costello (2013), MOODLE was started by a computer science graduate, Martin Dougiamas, in a computer server room of an Australian university in 1999. Ever since the first version of MOODLE was

released, its source code has been available and open to anyone. The MOODLE platform is a type of e-learning platform used in the teaching process (Kumar et al., 2020).

Statement of the Problem

The biology curriculum is wide, there is always a lot to cover within the short period of a semester. Blended learning through the use of ICT has potentials to significantly increase the content coverage if adopted. Despite the aforementioned benefits of Moodle-LMS usage and ICT in general and the fact that LMS has been in full force over a decade ago, Nigeria Universities is one specific context in which Moodle-LMS adoption and usage has been met with many barriers rooted in cultural and moral discourses (Brophy, 2016). Many implementation barriers have been identified in various studies, one of such barriers as pointed out by Chuang (2021) was lack of technical skills which may be linked to their attitude towards LMS usage. Cigdem and Ozturk (2016) made a case that lecturers as well as students “play important roles in specifying the effectiveness, success or inefficacy, and adoption of the e-learning systems, so predicting the perception students have towards the use of Moodle-LMS is essential prior to its adoption”. It is to this regard that Universities in Ilorin, Nigeria attitude towards use of Moodle-LMS forms the crux of the study.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the Perception of Biology Education students on the Use of Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin, Nigeria. Specifically, this study:

1. determined Biology Education students’ Perception of Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin
2. ascertained Biology Education students’ Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin, Ilorin
3. examined the influence of Biology Education students’ Gender on their Perception of Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin, Ilorin
4. determined the influence of Biology Education students’ Gender on their Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin, Ilorin

Research Questions

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance in this study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Perception of Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin, Ilorin

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin, Ilorin

Methodology

This study adopted a survey method of descriptive research. A researcher-designed questionnaire was used to collect data and obtain relevant information needed for the study. The target population for this study was Biology Education students of University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria. The instrument adopted for data collection was a self-constructed questionnaire titled “students’ Perception of the Use of Moodle-LMS for Learning in the University of Ilorin, Ilorin”. The questionnaire is divided into 2 major parts A and B. Section A will contain the Demographic information of the respondents, section B contains questions on the Perception of and Use of Moodle-LMS for Learning.

Validation of the Research Instrument was to establish by presenting the drafts copy of the questionnaire to supervisor for clarity, appropriateness, correctness, commensuration of the question with the topic, the research and other criteria for the validation of the text. Then the instruments will further be assessed by three lecturers in the Department of Educational Technology after correction will be effected for validation.

The questionnaire is divided into section A and B. Section A collect information on demographic information of the Biology Education students, such as: level, faculty, course of study and gender while section B employed 4-point Likert response scale to elicit responses on Perception of Biology Education students toward Moodle-LMS for Learning. The 4-point Likert scale were rated 4 (Strongly Agree), 3 (Agree), 2 (disagree) and 1 (Strongly disagree).

The questionnaire was subjected to validity test by given it to three Lecturers in the department and the observations raised were effected before the production of the final draft. The questionnaire was then subjected to reliability test of Cronbach Alpha Coefficient which yielded 0.82. Random sampling technique was adopted to select 205 biology education students across all levels from the department of science education, University of Ilorin. Their responses were collated in preparation for statistical analysis. Research questions were answered through descriptive statistics of frequency count and research hypotheses will be analyzed using inferential statistics of t-test at 0.05 alpha level.

Results

Personal Data of the Respondents

Table 2 : Gender Distribution of Respondents

<i>S/N</i>	Items	Frequency	Percentage
<i>1</i>	Female	132	64.4
<i>2</i>	Male	73	35.6
	Total	205	100

Source : Fiels Survey, 2023

Table 2 shows the gender distribution of the respondents, it reveals that the Female respondent dominated the study with 132 (64.4%) while the Male respondent are 73 (35.6%).

Table 3: Level of Respondents

<i>S/N.</i>	Items	Frequency	Percentage
<i>1</i>	100 Level	61	29.8
<i>2</i>	200 Level	56	27.3
<i>3</i>	300 Level	60	29.3
<i>4</i>	400 Level	27	13.2
	Total	205	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3, reveals the respondent level of Education. The findings from this study indicated that out of the 205 respondents in the study, 61 (29.8%) are in 100 Level, 56 (27.3%) are in 200 level, 60 (29.3%) are in 300 Level, while 27 (13.2%) are in 400 Level University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Table 5: Percentage, Mean and Standard deviation scores of responses on Biology Education students' Perception of Moodle-LMS for Learning in the University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

S/N	Items	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	I can use Moodle for Learning	3.85	0.39	Agree
2	Using Moodle for learning can improve my attendance	3.68	0.57	Agree
3	I get more engaged with learning when using Moodle	3.68	0.57	Agree
4	Learning through Moodle improve my academic performance	3.67	0.58	Agree
5	I can use Moodle for personal learning	3.46	0.64	Agree
6	I can connect well with content being taught on Moodle	3.63	0.57	Agree
7	Using Moodle for learning can foster cooperation between lecturers and student	3.33	0.82	Agree
8	Using Moodle for learning can improve academic performance	3.39	0.80	Agree
9	Using Moodle for learning makes learning more interactive	3.46	0.64	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.57	0.62	

Table 5 shows the grand mean of 3.57 which is clearly above the Bench-Mark of 2.50 (agree) as well as standard deviation of 0.62 indicated that the respondents see Moodle-

LMS as a tool for Learning in University of Ilorin. Mean score of 3.85 shows that majority of the respondents will like to use LMS for Learning. Mean score of 3.68 which is also greater than the mid score of 2.50 agrees with the item that using LMS for Learning increases their Learning attendance. Higher number of respondents also believes that using LMS for Learning allow them to connect effectively with their peer and content being taught with the mean score of 3.46. Most respondents also believe that using LMS for Learning improve their academic performance with a means score of 3.39.

Research Question 2: What is the level of Biology Education students' Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS in the University of Ilorin?

Table 6: Percentile Analysis on Biology Education students' Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS in the University of Ilorin, Nigeria

S/N.	Items	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	<i>Convenience and accessibility of Moodle for learning creates a positive attitude in learners</i>	3.44	0.58	Agree
2.	<i>Positive attitude towards Moodle for learning depends on the area of specialization</i>	3.07	0.98	Agree
3.	<i>Using Moodle for learning enhances student engagement with learning</i>	3.32	0.77	Agree
4.	<i>Moodle platform is easier to use for learning.</i>	3.73	0.42	Agree
5.	<i>I have used Moodle-LMS before and will love to use it for learning.</i>	3.41	0.59	Agree
6.	<i>Using Moodle for learning in online learning is more helpful than traditional classroom learning.</i>	3.46	0.64	Agree
7.	<i>Learning is more concrete and realistic through Moodle-LMS than other LMS platform.</i>	3.22	0.96	Agree

8.	<i>Learning content on Moodle are easily assessable and one can interact with it easily.</i>	3.29	0.92	Agree
9.	<i>Using Moodle for learning increase learner confidence and interaction with his peer</i>	3.46	0.64	Agree
Grand Mean		3.38	0.72	

Table 6 shows the grand mean of 3.38 which is clearly above the B of 2.50 (agree) as well as standard deviation of 0.72 indicated that the respondents are ready to Adopt Moodle-LMS in the University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria. Mean score of 3.73 which is the highest of the lot shows that majority of the respondents attested to the item that Moodle-LMS make learning much easier. Mean score of 3.44 which is also greater than the mid score of 2.50 agrees with the item that LMS is readily assessable and convenient to use. Higher number of participants also attest to have use LMS before will like to use it again for LMS for with the mean score of 3.41. Most participants also believe learning is more concrete and realistic through LMS with a means score of 3.22.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Perception of Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Table 7: t-test Analysis Showing Difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Perception of Moodle-LMS for Learning

Gender	No	Mean	Std Deviation	T	Df	P-value	Remark
<i>Male</i>	132	3.1515	0.9767				
				1.020	203	0.470	Accepted
<i>Female</i>	73	2.8493	0.9671				

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 7 shows the p-value on 203 Degree of Freedom, P-value (Sig, 2-tailed) 0.470 was greater than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Perception of Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin was accepted. This means there is no statistically proven significant difference in Undergraduate Male and Female perception of Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin.

Hypothesis Two:

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.

Table 8: t-test Analysis on Difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS for Learning

<i>Gender</i>	No	Mean	Std Deviation	T	Df	P-value	Remark
<i>Male</i>	132	3.3940	0.5917				
				1.244	203	0.154	Accepted
<i>Female</i>	73	3.4932	0.4756				

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 8, indicates that the p-value on 203 Degree of Freedom, P-value (Sig, 2-tailed) 0.154 was greater than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin was accepted. This means there is no

statistically proven significant difference in Biology Education students of University Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS for Learning based on Gender.

Summary of the Findings

1. The findings revealed that the respondents has high expectation on the Use of Moodle for Learning in University of Ilorin
2. The findings also revealed that most of the respondents are ready to adopt Moodle for Learning.
3. The findings also revealed that there is no significant difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Perception of Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin.
4. The findings also revealed there is no significant difference between Male and Female Biology Education students on their Readiness to Adopt Moodle-LMS for Learning in University of Ilorin

References

- Abdullah, M. S. (2017). Analysis of the Factors for the Successful E-Learning acceptance models and evaluation of the best fit for health industry organizations. *International Journal of Computer Science Engineering & Technology*, 1(11), 709-717.
- Awe, O. O. (2016). ICT4D Strategic Action Plan Implementation: *Status Update and illustrations Book*.
- Bervell, B., & Umar, I. N. (2018). Utilization decision towards LMS for blended learning in distance education: Modeling the effects of personality factors in exclusivity. *Knowledge Management and E-Learning*, 10(3), 309-333.
- Brophy, J. (2016). *Motivating students to learn* (3rd ed.). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Chuang, S. (2021). The applications of constructivist learning theory and social learning theory on adult continuous development. *Performance Improvement*, 60(3), 6–14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pfi.2196>
- Cigdem, H., & Ozturk, M. (2016). Factors affecting students' behavioral intention classroom: An experiment in online design collaboration hype or help? *International Journal of Arts & Sciences*, 11(1), 331-341.
- Costello, E. (2013) Opening up to open source: looking at how MOODLE was adopted in higher education. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open Distance and eLearning*, 28(3), 187-200, 2013.
- Patel, D. and Patel, H. I. (2017). Blended Learning in Higher Education using MOODLE Open Source Learning Management Tool. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*, 8(5) 439-441, 2017.
- Hui Hsu, H. (2012). The Acceptance of Moodle: An Empirical Study Based on UTAUT. *SciRes*, 2 (3), 44-46. Hakim A B 2016 Efektifitas Penggunaan E-Learning Moodle Google Classroom Dan Edmodo. *I-STATEMENT* 2(1), 44-46.
- Kumar, J.A., Bervell, B., & Osman, S. (2020). Google classroom: Insights from Malaysian higher education students' and instructors' experiences. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(5), 4175-4195. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10163-x>.
- Lee, J., Song, H.-D. & Hong, A. J. (2019). Exploring Factors, and Indicators for Measuring Students' Sustainable Engagement in e-Learning. *Sustainability* 2019, 11(9)85. Moodle, 2012; Available from: <http://moodle.org/> (2 March, 2012)

- Olorundare, A. S. (2023). *The goal of science education; Scientific Literacy and it aims*. SED 953 lecture notes (pp. 11-19). AL- Hikmah University Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Yilmaz, R., Karaođlan Yılmaz, F.G. & Cakmak, E. (2017).The impact of transactive memory system and interaction platform in collaborative knowledge construction on social presence and self-regulation. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 25(8), 949–969. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2016.1224905>.
- Zwain, A. A. A. (2019). Technological innovativeness and information quality as neoteric predictors of users' acceptance of learning management system: *An expansion of UTAUT2*. *Interactive Technology and Smart Education*, 16(3), 239-254. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITSE-09-2018-0065>